

Appendiceal Diverticulitis: Review and Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Appendiceal diverticulitis was first described in 1893 by Kelyneck, identifying diverticular sacs along the appendix. (1) It presents in congenital and acquired forms, the latter being more common and involving the entire wall of the appendix. (1) It is found in about 2% of all pathological appendix specimens, with a reported incidence between 0.014 and 1.9%. (2) In a literature review by Stive Vidovic, 34.5% of cases occurred in women and 65.5% in men, with a median age of 49 years for both sexes. (3) Preoperative diagnosis is challenging due to its similarity to classical appendicitis and poses a greater risk of perforation, as well as the synchronous formation of neoplasms such as mucinous adenomas and carcinoid tumors. (2) The clinical presentation of appendicitis usually includes pain in the lower right quadrant and right iliac fossa, fever, and leukocytosis. (3) This study presents the case of a 38-year-old male diagnosed with appendiceal diverticulitis, whose clinical presentation and preoperative diagnosis mimicked acute appendicitis.

KEYWORDS: Appendiceal Diverticulitis, APPENDICEAL DIVERTICULAE, APPENDICITY

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INTRODUCTION

Appendiceal diverticulitis was first described in 1893 by Kelyneck, identifying diverticular sacs along the appendix. (1) It presents in congenital and acquired forms, the latter being more common and involving the entire wall of the appendix. (1) It is found in about 2% of all pathological appendix specimens, with a reported incidence between 0.014 and 1.9%. (2) In a literature review by Stive Vidovic, 34.5% of cases occurred in women and 65.5% in men, with a median age of 49 years for both sexes. (3) Preoperative diagnosis is challenging due to its similarity to classical appendicitis and poses a greater risk of perforation, as well as the synchronous formation of neoplasms such as mucinous adenomas and carcinoid tumors. (2) The clinical presentation of appendicitis usually includes pain in the lower right quadrant and right iliac fossa, fever, and leukocytosis. (3) This study presents the case of a 38-year-old male diagnosed with appendiceal diverticulitis, whose clinical presentation and preoperative diagnosis mimicked acute appendicitis.

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CLINICAL CASE

IMAGE 1: Appendicitis is identified with an inflamed, necrotic distal border and multiple diverticula along the entire antimesenteric path.

IMAGE 2: Multiple diverticula are seen along the entire appendix

A 38-year-old male without significant chronic, surgical, or allergic history presented with abdominal pain for three days prior to emergency evaluation. He reported generalized pain rated 7/10 on the visual analog scale, associated with nausea but no vomiting. He had an unmeasured fever and self-medicated with Espaven (dimethicone). He had two episodes of diarrhea and denied urinary symptoms. He reported anorexia and no other associated symptoms. The patient came to our facility due to persistent pain.

On evaluation: he was in an antalgic position, conscious, oriented, with hydrated mucous membranes, adequately colored skin, reactive pupils, cylindrical neck, and centered trachea. Cardiopulmonary examination showed symmetric chest with normal ventilatory mechanics, well-ventilated lung fields, and rhythmic heart sounds with increased intensity and frequency. The abdomen was distended due to adipose tissue, showed muscle resistance and peritoneal irritation with positive Blumberg sign, present and normoactive peristalsis, positive McBurney, Dunphy, and Capurro signs, and negative Rovsing and Giordano signs. Limbs were intact with immediate capillary refill. The rest of the physical exam was unremarkable.

Lab results on 03.11.24: glucose 82, urea 27.6, creatinine 0.78, Cl 100, Ca 10.3, Na 139, K 3.8, P 3.1, Mg 1.7, Hb 15, Hct 43.4, WBC 17, Neutrophils 88.7%, Platelets 318, PT 15.1, INR 1.31, PTT 38. Clinical picture suggested acute appendicitis with an Alvarado score of 9, AIR score of 9 (without CRP), and RIPASA score of 14.

Hydration and antibiotic treatment were initiated with a third-generation cephalosporin and anaerobic coverage with metronidazole. The patient was admitted to the OR for open appendectomy and surgical exploration on 04.11.25. Intraoperative findings included a retrocecal appendix measuring 7x2 cm, fibrin layers in the distal third, apparent diverticular sacs along the antimesenteric border of the appendix (Images 1 and 2), and a local collection of 5 cc of seropurulent fluid. A routine appendectomy was performed without surgical complications.

Postoperative monitoring showed no complications, with the patient tolerating oral intake and having normal bowel movements without systemic inflammatory response signs. He was discharged on the second hospital day with outpatient management including analgesics and antibiotics with anaerobic coverage. Unfortunately, a pathology report for microscopic diagnosis was not available.

DISCUSSION

Appendiceal diverticulosis and diverticulitis are extremely rare entities with a reported incidence of 0.004% to 2.1%. (2) They clinically mimic appendicitis but carry a higher risk of perforation (33.3% vs. 9.88%). (4) Acute appendicitis more commonly affects younger individuals, whereas diverticular disease is more

frequent in older patients. (4) Clinical presentation may vary, including intermittent pain that can be misdiagnosed as chronic appendicitis. It is generally an incidental finding, and treatment is the same as for acute appendicitis: surgical appendectomy. Imaging studies can be helpful, but in acute settings, contrast-enhanced CT shows tissue enhancement that may obscure diverticula due to periappendicular inflammation. Thus, definitive diagnosis is made by direct observation and histopathology. (5) Among potential complications, increased perforation risk is noteworthy. A study published in the Journal of the Korean Surgical Society in 2013 reported no sex differences among patients, with an average age of 49 years and a 25-year age range between groups with and without diverticulitis. Patients with appendiceal diverticulitis had symptoms lasting an average of 3.6 days, with no statistically significant clinical differences. The perforation rate in this group was 65.8%, compared to 10.2% in the control group, and surgery duration, hospital stay, and need for drainage were all greater. (5) Given the potential for complications and the risk of mucinous neoplasm development, proper identification, protocolization, and treatment with appendectomy are crucial.

CONCLUSION

Due to its low incidence in the literature, proper medical approach, appropriate imaging studies, and the high risk of

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appendiceal perforation and postoperative complications, a high index of suspicion must be maintained. Prompt surgical treatment should not be delayed in cases like the one described above.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Informed consent was obtained for treatment, surgical procedures described in this case, photography, and eventual publication. Confidentiality of personal data was guaranteed. Ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the General Health Law were followed, taking necessary measures to protect patient identity. This case is relevant due to the opportunity it provides for learning and decisive, beneficial clinical decision-making. It is hoped this report will contribute to generating evidence and promoting best practices in similar cases

IMAGE 3: When identifying the inflamed appendix, diverticula are seen on the antimesenteric border

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